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CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL HEADS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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LORNA B. LEAL

April 29, 2023

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL
HEADS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

A Dissertation Submitted to the Faculty of the Institute of Graduate and
Advanced Studies in Partial Fulfillment for the Degree Doctor of
Education Major in Educational Management

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Urdaneta City University
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CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS

URDANETA CITY UNIVERSITY
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This research entitled “**CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL HEADS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC**” prepared and submitted by **LORNA B. LEAL** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree **Doctor of Education Major in Educational Management** has been examined and is hereby recommended for approval and acceptance.

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Abstract

This study determined the challenges encountered by public secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division during the Covid-19 pandemic and the coping mechanisms used by the School Heads to manage the challenges. It used the descriptive-correlational research design.

This study found out that in the profile variables of the respondent-School Heads, majority are females, 51 and above years old, Master's degree holders with 11-15 years in service. Majority of the respondents are Principal III-IV who are mostly trained in leadership and management relevant to the new normal. There are moderately high level of challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, and management of resources. A high level of challenges was encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along accountability and continuous improvement.

Findings also show that the level of coping mechanisms of the School Heads to manage the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic along production of instructional/ modular materials, training of teachers, and provision of technological tools are high. A moderately high level of coping mechanism was also found on school Heads' management during the pandemic along production, distribution and retrieval of modules. There is a significant relationship that exists on the level of challenges encountered by the School Heads along leadership and

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governance, and the profile variables, sex and position. A significant relationship also exists between the level of challenges encountered along curriculum and learning and the School Heads' highest educational attainment. Further, a significant relationship exists between the level of challenges encountered along management of resources and the profile variable, age.

Keywords: Challenges, Coping Mechanisms, Leadership and Governance, Curriculum & Learning, Accountability & Continuous Improvement, Management of Resources

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CERTIFICATION OF INTELLECTUAL HONESTY

This is to certify that all sources used in this study have been properly acknowledged and duly cited with utmost diligence. This is to certify further that this research is an original undertaking and has neither been submitted for another degree nor has been copied from previous work.

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Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Covid-19 pandemic transformed our educational landscape and redirected our schools to the new normal of education. The pandemic has brought changes and challenges to the educational system. It has affected the usual flow of activities in the schools and in the whole community at large. Everyone must adjust to the situation of lockdowns, social distancing and new modes of learning. Teachers have to shift their lessons and learners must follow. Schools were closed, teachers have to report in limited time, and definitely no learners are allowed to come to school. School Heads got the biggest challenge of making all things happen in school despite the pandemic. They must ensure that teaching-learning must be done in the safest way possible and most convenient to everyone. But, the sudden switch in the delivery of lessons from face to face to other modes of learning such as modular and online learning due to the coronavirus-19 pandemic has left educators with difficulty transitioning their traditional pedagogy to active online learning pedagogy (Aginaldo, 2021). In this pandemic the delivery of basic services in education all depends on the leadership and management skills of School Heads.

Since the pandemic caused hindrances to face-to-face education (Abbas, 2021), the Department of Education instituted DepEd Order No. 12 series 2020, which formulated new learning delivery modalities at all levels as represented in

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the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). In line with this, School Heads also crafted and aligned their School Learning Continuity Plan. Further, DepEd Memorandum No. 50, series 2020 entitled DepEd Professional Development (PD) Priorities of Teachers and school Leaders for SY 2020-2023, the school leaders must undergo the different professional development in support of the operationalization of the school considering Covid-19. The domains included are the following: 1) Leading strategically; 2) Managing school Operations and Resources; 3) focusing on Teaching and Learning; 4) Developing self and others; and 5) Building connections. In here, it can be seen that the School Heads are needed the most not only to perform their usual tasks but to ensure that schools can still manage its operations and activities despite this pandemic. The need then of transformational leadership style among school principals are needed (Ancho, 2020).

Different learning modalities were presented but most of the public schools opted to use the printed self-learning modules. Few used the online learning because of accessibility to internet connection, availability of gadgets, and financial factors. School Heads have to be oriented with the new processes to be implemented to ensure that there will still be teaching-learning that will take place in schools. They would then orient their teachers and stakeholders on how things will go about, of their contributions and roles as part of the new normal, and how the children can still learn. To everyone, schools are expected to offer provision so

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it becomes central to development, learning, and achievement of the children and youth for whom they are responsible (Francisco and Barcelona, 2020).

Teaching and learning is frustrating and challenging to everyone during the pandemic. In the implementation of teaching-learning process in schools, the school heads must see to it that the new processes are being observed. In the study of Agayon et al. (2021), they found out that teachers are greatly challenged in terms of learning' quality transfer, module distribution and retrieval, students' difficulties in following instruction, power disruption, internet connection, and health risks posed by the pandemic.

Likewise, based on the results the study of Aginaldo (2021), inconsistent internet connection, lack of space and equipment, low-level participation of students, and difficulty correcting students' execution were among the obstacles they faced in online classes. Minimal transfer of skills and knowledge to students has become the major disadvantage of conducting online classes while comfort and safety unfold to be its advantages.

Also, the study of Belgica et al. (2020) found out that physical and digital distractions, technological and technical difficulties, institutional and academic issues, and personal and psychological barriers are the challenges that the pupils encounter during online classes. They recommended designating a specific area or gadget for online classes, providing intensive training on how to navigate online the online learning platforms, maintaining an open communication between

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teachers and students, using flipped classroom instruction, strengthening parent-teacher partnership in ensuring guidance while learning from home, and providing guidance and counseling to stakeholders as strategies suited to the new normal e-learning modality.

Through all of these situations, the School Head is accounted to be the most responsible in assuring the smooth flow of teaching-learning process and other operational activities in schools. The study of Aytac (2020) on the problems faced by school administrators during Covid-19 pandemic included the low learning motivation of students, parents' inability to create a learning environment at home, and the lack of access to live broadcasts from the EBA/TV education portal. The majority of the school administrators observed that teachers were reluctant to teach in live lectures using the education portal or other programs for various reasons and their motivation gradually decrease in the process. It is observed that half of the administrators did not have emergency action plan regarding the pandemic process. School administrators stated that skills of technology leadership and crisis management are important requirements during the pandemic process.

The School Heads may propose programs and trainings to ensure smooth delivery of basic services in schools. In the study of Bautista et al. (2021), distance learning has become the sole modality of the teaching and learning process in the Philippines due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The study found out that majority of the respondents received adequate support from their respective schools in terms of

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capacity building, technical and data privacy matters, systems of information dissemination, and online learning management. Financial and emotional support mechanisms are two areas for improvement. The common problems encountered included motivating the students, using ICT, managing the time allotted for online sessions, and evaluating the learners' knowledge. The teachers were also looking for more free resources and tools, webinars to share ideas and challenges, and professional development.

Good leadership skills among school heads has something to do not only of the present situation in schools but also of immediate and emergency situations. Francisco et al. (2020) on the emergence of a situational leadership during Covid-19 pandemic, found out that: (1) new normal leadership is the ability to be adaptive while staying strong with one's commitment; (2) it is about being an effective instructional decision maker; (3) a leader who is a good planner, vigilant, and initiator.

A recent study defined new normal leadership in terms of a focus on people, human resources, mentoring, learning, healing emotions; a leader who is facilitator, never top down, conscious of leadership development; a healthy working environment, respect change of ideas, a creative class; trust through sharing, teams, embracing equality, diversity, slack, tolerance; vision, and commitment to the vision, through talent, technology, storytelling; and a dynamic interplay between all stakeholders, employees, customers, investors, shareholders (Millar, 2019).

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The study of Villar et al. (2021) assessed the relationship between the school heads' leadership practices, administrative disposition, and readiness of the public school principals for school year 2020-2021. Findings revealed that the school heads' leadership practices and the administrative disposition were highly practiced during the new normal in the education system. In terms of the readiness of the public schools, the results revealed that the schools are much ready. The school heads' leadership practices and administrative disposition related the readiness of the school. The school heads' leadership practices in terms of resiliency in stress management and the administrative disposition in terms of inclusivity and accommodative significantly predicted the readiness of the public schools.

Further, the study of Martinez et al. (2021) revealed the degree that administrators defined their work experiences during this period, based on four distinct perspectives, including: (a) structural, (b) symbolic, (c) political, and (d) human resources. Also, the study revealed administrator perceptions of equity and access among various constituents at their school, including teachers, support staff, students, parents, and members of the broader school community. Further, using open systems theory as a theoretical perspective, the study revealed six emergent themes that related to their work while opening school during a world crisis: (a) technology access/instruction, (b) informational/procedural ambiguity, (c) resource dependency, (d) policy adaptability, (e) stakeholder disposition, and (f) methods of communication.

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The lockdown in the Philippines started on March 2020 but the present pandemic situation is still not stable. While we have already started with the implementation of limited face-to-face classes in schools, there are still increasing alert levels in other places. It's more than two years but we are still unsure if we can go back to the old normal. The appearance of new cases until today even if in minimal numbers alarm the public and would not risk the health of their children. In view of the above-mentioned citations, the researcher conducted a study that will focus on the challenges and coping mechanisms of school Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic. This study specifically assessed the challenges and coping mechanisms of School Heads in Pangasinan II Division in region I. Further, it assesses significant relationships that have been the basis of an action plan that might be useful in facing still the present times and future similar situations such as this Covid-19 pandemic.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Fiedler's contingency theory. It is one of the contingency theories that states that effective leadership depends not only on the style of leading but on the control over a situation. There needs to be good leader-member relations, task with clear goals and procedures, and the ability for the leader to mete out rewards and punishments. Lacking these three in the right combination and context will result in leadership failure. Fiedler created the least preferred co-

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worker (LPC) scale, where a leader is asked what traits can be ascribed to the co-worker that the leader likes the least.

Fiedler's contingency theory is a qualification or type of contingency theory. Contingency theories in general state that the effectiveness of leadership depends upon the situation, and there are numerous factors, such as the nature of the task, leader's personality, and make-up of the group being led. For a more comprehensive discussion of contingency theories in general.

Fiedler's contingency theory emphasized the leader's personality, or psychological disposition, is a main variable in her/his ability to lead, and said that how the group receives the leader, the task involved, and whether the leader can actually exert control over the group are the three principle factors that determine how successful the leader-led arrangement will be (<https://www.leadership-central.com/fiedler%27s-contingency-theory.html>).

The reviewed theory is related to this study as it involves actions which served as basis for the problems of this study. The study will assess the challenges and coping mechanisms of School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic. On the challenges it will centralized on their management on curriculum and learning, leadership and governance, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources. To dig deeper, the researcher will conduct an interview on the coping mechanisms employed by the Secondary School Heads. All of which will be the basis for a plan of action that could be useful in the future where similar

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situations may be encountered. This theory will be used in assessing the challenges and coping mechanisms of Secondary School Heads in the Division of Pangasinan

II.

Figure 1. Fiedler's Contingency Theory of Leadership

Paradigm of the Study

The independent variable was the profile of the respondent – Secondary School Heads from the Division of Pangasinan II. The profile included their sex,

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age, years in service, position, highest educational attainment, and relevant trainings attended. Through the use of a survey questionnaire, the study concentrated on the analysis of data that were gathered from all the respondents.

Figure 2. Paradigm of the Study

The dependent variables included the challenges encountered by the School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along curriculum and learning, leadership and governance, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources. The study sought significant relationships on the challenges and the

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School Heads' selected profile variables. A plan of action was proposed base from the results of the survey and interview.

Statement of the Problem

This study assessed the challenges and coping mechanisms of School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Within this scope, this study specifically aimed to address the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the School Heads in terms of:
 - a. age;
 - b. sex;
 - c. years in service;
 - d. position;
 - e. highest educational attainment; and
 - f. trainings attended?

2. What is the level of challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along:
 - a. leadership and governance;
 - b. curriculum and learning;
 - c. accountability and continuous improvement; and
 - d. management of resources?

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3. What is the level of coping mechanisms used by School Heads to cope with the challenges?
 - a. production of instructional/ modular materials
 - b. training of teachers
 - c. provision of technological tools
 - d. production, distribution and retrieval of modules
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the respondents' profile variables?
5. What plan of action may be proposed for further development of teaching-learning in the schools?

Research Hypotheses

This study tested the following research hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

1. There is a significant relationship between the level of challenges by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the respondents' profile variables.

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Chapter 2

Methodology

This chapter presents the method and procedure to be used in the conduct of this study. It deals with the research design used, population and locale of the study, data collection instrument, data collection procedure and treatment of data.

Research Design and Strategy

This study used descriptive method of research. The descriptive method of research was used to help provide answers to the questions of who, what, when, where, and how associated with a particular research problem; a descriptive study cannot conclusively answers to why. Descriptive research is used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena and to describe “what exists” with respect to variables or conditions in a situation (Betensky, 2015). The descriptive method of research is appropriate with this study because it will seek answers to a particular problem and describes the needed variables. This method of research involves comparison or contrast and attempts to discover significant differences and relationships between existing variables.

This study secured evidence concerning current or existing situations. The study used the standard survey method through the questionnaire. The researcher prepared the survey and interview questionnaire so that respondents and readers can understand the information contained in the data. The questionnaire was uploaded in google forms.

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Population and Locale of the Study

The respondents of this study included the Secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division in the province of Pangasinan. The researcher used a total enumeration of the 123 secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division as respondents of this study.

Data Collection Instruments

This study used the survey questionnaire as a data gathering tool. The first part of the questionnaire checklists included the personal attributes of the respondents and it was prepared based on the researcher's experiences, observations, and readings. The part on the challenges encountered and coping mechanisms used by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic, the researcher crafted the indicators based on present and emerging situations. The data gathered were handled with utmost confidentiality. The items of the questionnaire adopted the four-point Likert-scale type of responses.

There was a validation of the instrument to ascertain that every question is clearly understood and within the experiences of the actual respondents of the study. This ensures that the respondents did not find difficulty in answering the questionnaire, and the data gathered were valid and reliable. The validity of the data-gathering instrument was described in terms of the following scale values with the corresponding descriptive equivalence:

Mean Scale Value	Point Value	Descriptive Rating
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3.26 – 4.00	4	Highly Valid
2.51 – 3.25	3	Valid
1.76 – 2.50	2	Moderately Valid
1.0 – 1.75	1	Not Valid

The questionnaire was evaluated and refined also by members of the researcher's panel and other research experts. Finalization of the questionnaire was based on the suggestions, and after the approval of the committee on oral examination. The incorporation of all suggestions of the research experts were included in the final draft.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher secured permission from the authorities of the division of Pangasinan II before administering the research. Specifically, it sought the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher also requested the respondents to answer the questionnaire in google forms after the approval of the proper authorities' concern. The conduct was possible through the help of the division research and planning officer and other personnel who were concerned in the study.

The purpose and objectives of the study were clearly explained. Utmost confidentiality was assured to avoid inhibitions from the respondents in accomplishing the questionnaire. The research subjects were asked to choose their

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preferred response by checking or supplying the needed information in the blank spaces provided for.

Treatment of Data

The data gathered through the questionnaire were subjected to appropriate tools to answer the specific problems of the study. It was tallied, organized, tabulated, and presented in textual and tabular form.

1. Frequency counts and percentages were used in determining the profile of the respondents.
2. Weighted mean was used to determine the challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic. The following scale/legend was also used to interpret and analyze the data to be gathered.

Mean Scale Value	Point Value	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	4	High	The challenges encountered by SHs affected their management to a high extent
2.51-3.25	3	Moderately High	The challenges encountered by SHs affected their management to a moderately high extent
1.76-2.50	2	Low	The challenges encountered by SHs affected their management to a low extent
1.00-1.75	1	Very Low	The challenges encountered by SHs affected their management to a very low extent

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3. Weighted mean was used to determine the appropriateness of the coping mechanisms used by School Heads to cope with the challenges. The following scale/legend was used to interpret and analyze the data to be gathered.

Mean Scale Value	Point Value	Descriptive Rating
3.26 – 4.00	4	High
2.51 – 3.25	3	Moderately High
1.76 – 2.50	2	Low
1.00 – 1.75	1	Very Low

4. Pearson r Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to determine significant relationship between the level of challenges encountered by the School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the respondents' profile variables

The data of the study were processed, organized, and summarize through the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (2021). The data were summarized, analyzed, and interpreted in terms of frequencies, ranking, percent, and measures of central tendencies and variability. Being descriptive, the researcher also attempted to be more comprehensive, qualitative and critical in making the analysis.

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Chapter 3

Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the data collected, statistical analyses made, and the interpretation of the salient findings. The result of the analyses of the data were organized in tabular form and sequenced in the order of the specific research problems that they are intended to answer.

Profile of the School Heads

Table 1 shows the data on the profile variables, sex, age, highest educational attainment, position, years in service and number of trainings attended.

Sex. The results show that among the respondents, there are 54 males or 43.9 percent and 69 females or 56.1 percent. This means that the majority of the School Heads in public secondary schools in Pangasinan II division are females.

This is a typical situation in the educational field which is mostly dominated by females but it is also starting to change because more males are now joining the teaching course. This can be easily seen in the slight difference in the number of female against male School Heads.

Age. Most of the respondent-school heads, 60 of them or 48.8 percent belong to the 51 and above age brackets. The second largest group, 57 of them or 46.3 percent belong to the 41-50 age brackets. There are only 6 of respondent-school heads or 4.9 percent who belong to the 30 and below age brackets.

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Table 1

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents across the Variables Sex, Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Years in Service, Position, and Number of Trainings Attended

Variable	Variable Category	Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	54	43.9
	Female	69	56.1
	Total	123	100.0
Age	30 and below	6	4.9
	41-50	57	46.3
	51 and above	60	48.8
	Total	123	100.0
Highest Educational Attainment	Master's Unit Earner	3	2.4
	Master's Degree Holder	67	54.5
	Doctorate Unit Earner	31	25.2
	Doctorate Degree Holder	22	17.9
Years in Service	Total	123	100.0
	5 years and below	18	14.6
	6-10 years	7	5.7
	11-15 years	35	28.5
	16-20 years	35	28.5
	21 years and above	28	22.8
Position	Total	123	100.0
	Teacher-In-Charge	6	4.87
	Head Teacher I-VI	7	5.70
	Assistant Principal	6	4.87
	Principal I-II	22	17.89
	Principal III-IV	82	66.67
No. of Trainings Attended	Total	123	100.0
	3 and below	4	3.25
	4-6	13	10.57
	7-9	36	29.27
	10 and above	70	56.91

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Highest Educational Attainment. The majority of the coaches-respondents, 67 of them or 54.5 percent are Master's degree holders. There are 31 or 25.2 percent who are Doctorate unit earners. 22 or 17.9 percent are Doctorate degree holders, and only 3 or 2.4 percent of the respondents are Master's unit earners.

The result only implies that the respondent School Heads aim for their professional development as it can be seen that majority of them have pursued post-graduate studies. Hence, they look forward of improving themselves in their chosen field or career path.

Years in Service. 35 or 28.5 percent belonged to 11-15 years in service and another 35 or 28.5 percent belonged to 16-20 years in service. 28 or 22.8 percent have 21 years and above and 18 or 14.6 percent have 5 years and below in service. There are only 7 or 5.7 percent who have rendered 6-10 years in service.

The data implies that majority of the School Heads are experienced and on their prime in the educational field.

Number of Trainings. Majority of the School Heads, 70 or 56.91 percent had 10 and above number of trainings. 36 or 29.27 percent have 7-9 relevant trainings, 13 or 10.57 percent have 4-6 relevant trainings, and only 4 or 3.25 percent have 3 and below trainings.

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The data implies that more than half of the School Heads have enough trainings and also implies that a quarter of them need enough trainings.

Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic

Tables 2, 3, 4 and 5 show the challenges encountered by the School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources.

Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic along Leadership and Governance

Table 2 shows the challenges encountered by the secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance

Table 2 shows that the development of a long term training and development program with regards to leadership and governance is highly challenging among the School Heads with a mean, 3.34. Hence, the challenges of the School Heads affected their management to a high extent. While, the rest of the indicators in table 2 shows a moderately high challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic. The “school and the community collaboratively define the structure and the roles and responsibilities of each member in the organization,” 3.16 mean and the “development plan (SIP) is regularly reviewed by the school community to keep it responsive and relevant to

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Table 2

Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic
along Leadership and Governance

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. The development plan (SIP) developed collaboratively by the stakeholders of the school and the community.	2.98	Moderately High
2. The development plan (SIP) is regularly reviewed by the school community to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges and opportunities.	3.04	Moderately High
3. The school is organized by a clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared leadership and governance and define the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders.	2.90	Moderately High
4. A leadership network facilitates communication between and among school and community leaders for informed-decision- making and solving of school-community wide learning problems.	2.98	Moderately High
5. A long-term program is in operation that addresses the training and development needs of school and community leaders.	3.02	Moderately High
6. The school and community collaboratively define the structure and the roles and responsibilities of each member in the organization	3.16	Moderately High
7. The development of a long term training and development program	3.34	High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.06	Moderately High

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately High
1.76 – 2.50	Low
1.00 – 1.76	Very Low

emerging needs, challenges and opportunities, 3.04 mean. This means that the challenges affected the management of the School Heads to a moderate extent. This implies that the School Heads have made a definition of their roles and

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responsibilities during the pandemic. This complements the study of Francisco et al. (2020) on the emergence of a situational leadership during Covid-19 pandemic, found out that: (1) new normal leadership is the ability to be adaptive while staying strong with one's commitment; (2) it is about being an effective instructional decision maker; (3) a leader who is a good planner, vigilant, and initiator.

The overall weighted mean, 3.06 only shows that the challenges encountered by the secondary School Heads in the division of Pangasinan II during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance is moderately high. This means that the challenges encountered by the School Heads during the pandemic affected their management to a moderately high extent. This result implies that the secondary school heads had a moderately high encounter on the challenges posted during the covid-19 pandemic.

Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic along Curriculum and Learning

Table 3 shows the challenges encountered by the secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division during the Covid-19 pandemic along curriculum and learning.

The indicator, "methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible, and aimed at developing self-directed learners," got the highest mean, 3.49 described as high level of challenge encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along curriculum and learning. This means that there is a high level of challenge encountered among the

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school heads with respect to developing self-directed learners. The result implies that the School Heads perceived that along curriculum and learning, there is a big challenge with respect to methods and resources. This result complements the study of Dayagbil et al. (2021), that during school lockdowns, the teachers made adjustments in teaching and learning designs guided by the policies implemented by the institution. Most of the students had difficulty complying with the learning activities and requirements due to limited or no internet connectivity. Emerging themes were identified from the qualitative responses to include trajectory for flexible learning delivery, the role of technology, the teaching and learning environment, and the prioritization of safety and security.

The overall weighted mean show that there is moderately high level of challenges encountered by the School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along curriculum and learning. This means that the challenges encountered by the School Heads along curriculum and learning affected their management only to a moderate extent. This only shows that teachers had encountered challenges which can be manageable at their own level or can be referred to their higher authorities once they cannot manage or handle the challenges on their own level.

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Table 3

Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic
along Curriculum and Learning

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. The curriculum provides for the development needs of all types of the learners in the community.	2.99	Moderately High
2. The implemented curriculum is localized to make it more meaningful to the learners and applicable to life in the community.	3.00	Moderately High
3. A representative group of school and community stakeholders develop methods and materials for developing creative thinking problem solving.	2.93	Moderately High
4. The learning systems are regularly and collaboratively monitored by the community using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners.	3.03	Moderately High
5. Appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved and assessment results are contextualized to the learner and local	3.16	Moderately High
6. Learning managers and facilitators (teachers, administrators, and community members) nurture values and environments that are protective to all children and demonstrate behaviours consistent to the organization's vision, mission and goals.	3.15	Moderately High
7. Methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible, and aimed at developing self-directed learners. Learners are equipped	3.49	High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.11	Moderately High

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately High
1.76 – 2.50	Low
1.00 – 1.76	Very Low

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Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic along Accountability and Continuous Improvement

Table 4 shows the challenges encountered by the secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division during the Covid-19 pandemic along accountability and continuous improvement.

Table 4 shows that there is a high level of challenges encountered with regards to the indicator, “the accountability system is owned by the community and is continuously enhanced to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community,” 3.99 mean. This only shows that the community has a significant role in the school most especially in the development and betterment of processes and policies. This means that the challenges encountered by the School Heads affected their management to a high extent. It implies that the School Heads should create mutual responsibilities and accountabilities with the community to where the school is situated. This findings corresponds to the Martinez et al. (2021) revealing that the administrator perceptions of equity and access among various constituents at their school including teachers, support staff, students, parents and members of the broader school community.

The overall weighted mean, 3.39, indicates a general perception that all the challenges encountered by the School Heads during the pandemic along accountability and continuous improvement are high. This result only implies that

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the School Heads perceived that they have met these challenges and had to resolve them head on in order to proceed with the new normal in education.

Table 4

Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic along Accountability and Continuous Improvement

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Roles and responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders.	3.12	Moderately High
2. Achievement of goals is recognized based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system; gaps are addressed through appropriate action.	3.24	Moderately High
3. The accountability system is owned by the community and is continuously enhanced to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community.	3.99	High
4. Accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes are inclusive and collaboratively developed and agreed upon.	3.26	High
5. Appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved and assessment results are contextualized to the learner and local situations and the attainment of the relevant life skills.	3.35	High
6. Stakeholders are engaged in the development and operation of an appropriate accountability assessment system.	3.35	High
7. School-community developed performance assessment is practiced and is the basis for improving monitoring and evaluation systems, providing monitoring and evaluation systems, providing technical assistance, and recognizing and refining plans.	3.41	High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.39	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 High

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<i>2.51 – 3.25</i>	<i>Moderately High</i>
<i>1.76 – 2.50</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>1.00 – 1.76</i>	<i>Very Low</i>

Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic along Management of Resources

Table 5 shows the challenges encountered by the secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division during the Covid-19 pandemic along management of resources.

Table 5 shows that the School Heads have a high level of challenges encountered on “an established system of partnership is managed and sustained by stakeholders for continuous improvement of resource management,” 3.38 mean. This means that the School Heads have encountered challenges along management of resources which affected their management to a high extent. This implies that the School Heads met challenges along the sustainability of established partnership with stakeholders. The pandemic had lessen the support from stakeholders most likely, they also have they have their own needs to prioritize before they can reach out with the school or the community.

The overall mean, 3.25 shows that there is a moderately high level of challenge encountered along the management of resources. This implies that the resources usually supported by partners or stakeholders are still maximized even if there is the presence of pandemic. Hence, the School Heads have shown that they are always proactive on situations like the pandemic. This result affirms the study of Bautista et al. (2021), distance learning has become the sole modality of the

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teaching and learning process in the Philippines due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The study found out that majority of the respondents received adequate support from their respective schools in terms of capacity building, technical and data privacy matters, systems of information dissemination, and online learning management.

Table 5
Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic
along Management of Resources

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Regular resource inventory is collaboratively undertaken by learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization.	3.08	Moderately High
2. A regular dialogue for planning and resource programming, that is accessible and inclusive, continuously engage stakeholders and support implementation of community education plans.	3.25	Moderately High
3. In place is a community-developed resource management system that drives appropriate behaviours of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.	3.30	High
4. Regular Monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management are collaboratively developed and implemented by the learning managers, facilitators and community stakeholders.	3.18	Moderately High
5. There is a system that manages the network and linkages, which strengthens and sustains partnerships for improving resource management.	3.28	High
6. Resource inventories are systematically developed and stakeholders are engaged in a collaborative process to make decisions on resource allocation and mobilization.	3.31	High
7. An established system of partnership is managed and sustained by the stakeholders for continuous improvement of resource management.	3.38	High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.25	Moderately High

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	<i>High</i>
2.51 – 3.25	<i>Moderately High</i>
1.76 – 2.50	<i>Low</i>
1.00 – 1.76	<i>Very Low</i>

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Summary on the Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic

Table 6 shows the summary of the challenges encountered by School Heads in Pangasinan II division during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Table 6 shows that only under the accountability and continuous improvement that there is a high level of challenges encountered. All the rest of the challenges encountered by the School Heads along leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, and management of resources show a moderately high level. This means that the School Heads have encountered challenges along leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, and management of resources that have affected their management to a moderately high extent. This implies that the challenges that were encountered by the School Heads during the pandemic are beyond their control but can be managed and resolved.

Table 6
Summary Table on the Challenges Encountered by School Heads

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Leadership and Governance	3.06	Moderately High
Curriculum and Learning	3.11	Moderately High
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	3.39	High
Management of Resources	3.25	Moderately High
OWM	3.20	Moderately High

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately High
1.76 – 2.50	Low
1.00 – 1.76	Very Low

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Coping Mechanisms Used by School Heads to Manage the Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic

Tables 7-10 shows the coping mechanisms used by the secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division to manage the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic along production of instructional/ modular materials, training of teachers, provision of technological tools, production, distribution and retrieval of modules.

Coping Mechanisms Used by School Heads to Manage the Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic Along production of Instructional/ Modular Materials

Table 7 shows that the indicator, “the teachers were given technical assistance in the preparation, distribution and retrieval of activity sheets or self-learning modules,” got the highest mean, 3.57. This means that the coping mechanism of School Heads to manage the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic along production of instructional or modular materials concentrated on giving assistance to teachers in their preparation, distribution and retrieval. This implies that School Heads have given priority to teachers’ needs and concerns on how they can produce instructional or modular materials necessary to be used by learners. Likewise, the School Heads see to it that the teaching-learning process must still be effective and efficient through the produced modular materials when face-to-face learning is not possible. This result is confirmed by Atencio et al. (2014), they pointed out that the delivery of learning is affected by the limited face-to-face

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interaction and schools adapt mostly the modular method of learning. Hence, learning and the desired outcomes should be achieved regardless of the situation.

Table 7

Coping Mechanisms Used by School Heads to Manage the Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic along Production of Instructional/ Modular Materials

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. The educational needs of learners were provided by the school	3.51	High
2. The teachers received their needed materials in the delivery of basic education services	3.45	High
3. The learners are given enough reading materials to help them cope up with the new modes of learning	3.39	High
4. The teachers were supported in the contextualization and localization of the learning materials	3.28	High
5. The teachers were given technical assistance in the preparation, distribution and retrieval of activity sheets or self-learning modules	3.57	High
6. The teachers were supported with the necessary materials in the preparation and reproduction of activity sheets or self-learning modules	3.37	High
7. The teachers were able to meet increase in learning outcomes through the use of modules and online follow-up	3.40	High
8. All subjects were given equal attention in the preparation and reproduction of activity sheets or self-learning modules, and in the development of other learning materials	3.12	Moderately High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.39	High

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately High
1.76 – 2.50	Low
1.00 – 1.76	Very Low

Affirming this result is the study of Mamolo (2020), revealed that factors affecting the students' competence level revolve around teacher, environment, low-

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self-perception, and personal factors. Hence, this only shows that the School Heads have built strong ties with the community or stakeholders in carrying out the challenges on the needs for training of teachers with the present situation.

Table 8

Coping Mechanisms Used by School Heads to Manage the Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic along Training of Teachers

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. The school have provided trainings of teachers necessary in the pandemic situation	3.14	Moderately High
2. The teachers attended trainings that would enhance their skills in the use of the different learning modalities	3.47	High
3. The school specifically trained the teachers on the modes of learning being used in the school or division	3.18	Moderately High
4. The school provided technical support and assistance to the teachers	3.41	High
5. The teachers were given opportunities and choices in attending different trainings or webinars	3.15	Moderately High
6. The school have given regular updates to learners, parents and teachers on the changing situations and immediate programs or projects	3.15	Moderately High
7. The school coordinated the programs, projects, and new processes to all stakeholders	3.54	High
8. There are meetings, webinars and sessions conducted to ensure updates to teachers	3.28	High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.29	High

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	<i>High</i>
2.51 – 3.25	<i>Moderately High</i>
1.76 – 2.50	<i>Low</i>
1.00 – 1.76	<i>Very Low</i>

The overall weighted mean, 3.29 shows that there is a high level of coping mechanism implemented by the School Heads to manage the challenges of the

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Covid-19 pandemic along the needs on the training of teachers. This means that the School Heads despite of the struggle on the limited face-to-face activities found ways on how they can communicate the needs of the teachers and learners through modular on online manners. This implies the flexibility of School Heads in managing the challenges in a given new situation such as the pandemic.

Coping Mechanisms Used by School Heads to Manage the Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic along Provision of Technological Tools.

Tables 9 shows the coping mechanisms used by the secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division to manage the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic along provision of technological tools.

Table 9 shows that there is a high coping mechanism used by the School Heads to manage the challenges along the provision of technological tools through giving priority on the provision of technological materials and gadgets to learners, as well as on the purchase of printers, gadgets and equipment necessary for learning, 3.46 mean. This means that the School Heads knew the important needs of the teachers and learners to carry out their tasks during the pandemic. Likewise, they have given attention on how learners can cope with the situation by maximizing the limited help they can provide in terms of their needs of gadgets. This implies that the School Heads would source out for the needs of the learners if deemed necessary to address the needs and concerns of teachers and learners. Coinciding with these results, the findings of the study of Rahmadani et al. (2022)

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suggest insights into the impact of forced changes in teaching that could have implications for the professionalization of teacher education in terms of digitalization.

Table 9

Coping Mechanisms Used by School Heads to Manage the Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic along Provision of Technological Tools

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. The school through the division have provided technological materials and gadgets to learners	3.46	High
2. The school coordinated with the PTA and other school organization to support programs and projects necessary this pandemic	3.43	High
3. The LGU and potential stakeholders supported the school in the provision of technological tools	3.37	High
4. The school tapped the local officials in the municipalities, cities and province to help in providing technological tools	3.34	High
5. The school allotted technological tools' procurement through the MOOE	3.23	Moderately High
6. The school engaged the stakeholders in providing technological tools needed this pandemic	3.29	High
7. There are regular conduct of meetings to inform parents of the changes in the teaching-learning schedule and modalities most especially in the use of gadgets	3.30	High
8. The school purchased printers, gadgets and equipment necessary for learning	3.46	High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.36	High

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately High
1.76 – 2.50	Low
1.00 – 1.76	Very Low

The overall weighted mean, 3.36, shows that there is a high level of coping mechanism used by School Heads to manage the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic along provision of technological tools. This means that the School

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Heads with the change in environment to the new normal and limited face-to-face interaction, they have found resolutions to meet the needs of the teachers and learners. This implies that the School Heads are reactive and responsive to the needs of the times even if goes beyond the normal situation.

Coping Mechanisms Used by School Heads to Manage the Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic along Production, Distribution and Retrieval of Modules

Tables 10 shows the coping mechanisms used by the secondary School Heads of Pangasinan II division to manage the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic along production, distribution and retrieval of modules

Table 10 shows that the school Heads have provided trouble shooting mechanisms for learning modules that were not taken and returned on time, 3.47 mean. This means that there is a high level of coping mechanism to manage these kinds of challenges encountered by the School Heads on the production, distribution and retrieval of modules. Since, the division of Pangasinan II implemented the modular type of learning, the School Heads have prioritize the use of school resources to meet the needs of the modular learning modality. This implies that the School Heads have shown an aggressive and responsive attitude to cope with the challenges of the implemented learning modality. The study of Bustillo and Aguilos (2022) affirms this through the results in their study that most students were constrained by many challenges and struggles in complying with the tasks. These include internet connectivity problems, inadequate learning resources, difficulty understanding the module contents and assessment

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instructions, overloaded remote learning tasks, poor learning environment, and mental health problems.

The overall weighted mean, 3.17 shows a moderately high level of coping mechanisms used by the School Heads to manage the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic along production, distribution and retrieval of modules. This means that there are instances that the School Heads have met challenges that they cannot fully cope up with. There might be situations that are beyond their control and their limited resources cannot suffice. This implies that regardless of how strong the coping mechanism of the School Heads, there are also situations that they cannot easily manage though they can still surpass such inevitable situations.

Table 10

Coping Mechanisms Used by School Heads to Manage the Challenges of the Covid-19 Pandemic along Production, Distribution and Retrieval of Modules

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. The school resources were mostly used for the preparation and production of activity sheets or self-learning modules	3.45	High
2. The school provided an enough space necessary for the production of learning modules	3.24	Moderately High
3. The school coordinated with the local officials to help in the distribution and retrieval of modules	3.12	Moderately High
4. There were assigned pick-up and drop-off areas for the distribution and retrieval of modules	3.02	Moderately High
5. The school ensured regular announcement of schedules on the distribution and retrieval of modules	3.03	Moderately High

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6. The school required the teachers to create group chats with parents of learners to serve as communication venue for announcements and queries	3.07	Moderately High
7. The school maintains its partnership with the community, local officials and other potential stakeholders to give smooth flow on the reproduction, distribution and retrieval of modules	2.95	Moderately High
8. The school have provided trouble shooting mechanisms for learning modules that were not taken and returned on time	3.47	High
Overall Weighted Mean	3.17	Moderately High

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately High
1.76 – 2.50	Low
1.00 – 1.76	Very Low

Relationships between the Level of Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic and the Profile Variables

Table 11 presents the Pearson r Coefficients of Correlations between the level of challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the profile variables.

The data indicate that there is a significant relationship between the level of challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance, with the profile variables, sex.

The computed r-values, .165 yielded a .049 level of significance for the independent variable, sex and the dependent variable, challenges encountered during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance. The significant level of the Pearson r coefficient of correlation is below the significance level of

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0.05 set at the start of this study. Therefore, the hypothesis which states, “There is a significant relationship between the level of challenges by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the respondents’ profile variable, sex” is accepted. The result means that there is an indicated association between the dependent variable- the challenges encountered, and independent variable. In this result, it implies that the level of challenges encountered by the School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance have an indicated association with the sex of the respondents.

The data also indicate that there is a significant relationship between the level of challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance, with the profile variable, position. The computed r-values, .231 yielded a .010 level of significance for the independent variable, position and the dependent variable, level of challenges encountered along leadership and governance. The significant level of the Pearson r coefficient of correlation is below the significance level of 0.05 set at the start of this study. Therefore, the hypothesis which states, “There is a significant relationship between the level of challenges by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the respondents’ profile variable, position” is accepted. The result means that there is an indicated association between the dependent variable- challenges encountered, and independent variable, position. In this result, it implies that the level of

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challenges encountered by the School Heads during the pandemic along leadership and governance have an indicated association with the position of the respondents.

Further, the data also indicate that there is a significant relationship between the level of challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along curriculum and learning, with the profile variable, highest educational attainment. The computed r-values, .253 yielded a .005 level of significance for the independent variable, highest educational attainment and the dependent variable, level of challenges encountered along curriculum and learning. The significant level of the Pearson r coefficient of correlation is below the significance level of 0.05 set at the start of this study. Therefore, the hypothesis which states, “There is a significant relationship between the level of challenges by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the respondents’ profile variable, highest educational attainment” is accepted. The result means that there is an indicated association between the dependent variable- challenges encountered along curriculum and learning, and independent variable, highest educational attainment. In this result, it implies that the level of challenges encountered by the School Heads during the pandemic along leadership and governance have an indicated association with the highest educational attainment of the respondents. Hence, it can also imply that the School Heads have different levels of managing their challenges depending on their educational achievement.

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Furthermore, the data also indicate that there is a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along management of resources, with the profile variable, age. The computed r-values, .209 yielded a .021 level of significance for the independent variable, age and the dependent variable, level of challenges encountered along management of resources. The significant level of the Pearson r coefficient of correlation is below the significance level of 0.05 set at the start of this study. Therefore, the hypothesis which states, “There is a significant relationship between the level of challenges by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the respondents’ profile variable, age” is accepted.

Table 11
Relationships between the Level of Challenges Encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 Pandemic and the Profile Variables
N=123

Independent Variables	Pearson Correlations	Leadership & Governance	Curriculum & Learning	Accountability & Continuous Improvement	Management of Resources
Sex	r-Value	.165	-.097	-.063	-.041
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.049*	.287	.493	.652
Age	r-Value	-.021	-.046	.063	.209
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.817	.617	.489	.021*
Years in Service	r-Value	-.042	-.011	-.056	-.085
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.649	.908	.540	.351
Position	r-Value	.231	-.066	-.024	-.063
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010*	.470	.792	.490
Education	r-Value	-.050	.253	.036	-.040
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.581	.005*	.693	.658
Trainings	r-Value	-.048	.026	-.034	-.021
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.600	.776	.708	.818

*Significant at 0.05 level.

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The result means that there is an indicated association between the dependent variable- challenges encountered along management of resources, and independent variable, age. This implies that the level of challenges encountered by the School Heads during the pandemic along management of resources have an indicated association with the age of the respondents. Hence, it can also imply that the School Heads have managed their challenges depending on their age levels.

Along accountability and continuous improvement, there are no significant relationships found between the level of challenges encountered by the School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the profile variables. The significant level of the Pearson r coefficient of correlation is above the significance level of 0.05 set at the start of this study. Therefore, the hypothesis which states, “There is a significant relationship between the level of challenges by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic and the respondents’ profile variables” is rejected. This means that the challenges encountered along accountability and continuous improvement have no significant relationship with the profile of the respondents.

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Chapter 4

Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter shows the conclusions and recommendations that were derived from the analysis and interpretations of the findings of the study.

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions drawn from the salient findings of this study:

1. In the profile variables of the respondent-School Heads, majority are females, 51 and above years old, Master's degree holders with 11-15 years in service. Majority of the respondents too, are Principal III-IV who are mostly trained in leadership and management relevant to the new normal.
2. There are moderately high level of challenges encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, and management of resources. A high level of challenges was encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic along accountability and continuous improvement.
3. The level of coping mechanisms of the School Heads to manage the challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic along production of instructional/modular materials, training of teachers, and provision of technological tools are high. A moderately high level of coping mechanism was also

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found on school Heads' management during the pandemic along production, distribution and retrieval of modules.

4. There is a significant relationship that exists on the level of challenges encountered by the School Heads along leadership and governance, and the profile variables, sex and position. A significant relationship also exists between the level of challenges encountered along curriculum and learning and the School Heads' highest educational attainment. Further, a significant relationship exists between the level of challenges encountered along management of resources and the profile variable, age.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are the recommendations forwarded based on the findings and conclusions of this study:

1. It is strongly recommended that School Heads should continue their studies and should attend more relevant trainings to improve their leadership and management skills specifically in handling unexpected situations such as the Covid-19 pandemic.
2. Programs and projects in the schools must be developed and implemented to support the accountability and continuous improvement programs of the division.

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3. School Heads must strengthen the partnership programs of the schools to potential stakeholders in order to sustain the needs of the teachers and learners when unexpected situations arise.
4. Developmental program must be institutionalized and implemented specifically including profile variables that is consistent in managing the challenges and coping with unexpected situations.
5. There should be another study on the challenges and coping mechanisms with Covid-19 pandemic to further verify, complement or denies the result of the present study.

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CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS

APPENDIX A

URDANETA CITY UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF GRADUATE AND ADVANCED STUDIES
San Vicente West, Urdaneta City, Pangasinan

QUESTIONNAIRE

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL HEADS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Name (Optional) _____

I. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Directions: Please provide information about yourself by filling in the blanks provided. Put a check (✓) mark or the required data on the box or space provided to indicate your response.

1. Sex
 - Male
 - Female
2. Age
 - 30 and below
 - 31-40
 - 41-50
 - 51 and above
3. Years in service
 - 5 years and below
 - 6-10 years
 - 11-15 years
 - 16-20 years
 - 21 years and above
4. Position
 - Teacher In-Charge

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- Head Teacher I-III
 - Principal I-II
 - Principal III-IV
5. Highest Educational Attainment
- Bachelor's Degree
 - Master's Unit Earner
 - Master's Degree
 - Doctorate Unit Earner
 - Doctorate Degree
6. Relevant Trainings Attended
- 3 and below
 - 4-6
 - 7-9
 - 10 and above

II. CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY SCHOOL HEADS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Directions: Kindly check the number to assess the level of difficulties encountered by School Heads during the Covid-19 pandemic by using the scale below.

Legend:

- 4 High
- 3 Moderately High
- 2 Low
- 1 Very Low

A. LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE	4	3	2	1
1. The development plan (SIP) developed collaboratively by the stakeholders of the school and the community.				
2. The development plan (SIP) is regularly reviewed by the school community to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges and opportunities.				
3. The school is organized by a clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared leadership and governance and define the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders.				

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4. A leadership network facilitates communication between and among school and community leaders for informed-decision- making and solving of school-community wide learning problems.				
5. A long-term program is in operation that addresses the training and development needs of school and community leaders.				
6. The school and community collaboratively define the structure and the roles and responsibilities of each member in the organization				
7. The development of a long term training and development program				
B. CURRICULUM AND LEARNING	4	3	2	1
1. The curriculum provides for the development needs of all types of the learners in the community.				
2. The implemented curriculum is localized to make it more meaningful to the learners and applicable to life in the community.				
3. A representative group of school and community stakeholders develop methods and materials for developing creative thinking problem solving.				
4. The learning systems are regularly and collaboratively monitored by the community using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners.				
5. Appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved and assessment results are contextualized to the learner and local				
6. Learning managers and facilitators (teachers, administrators, and community members) nurture values and environments that are protective to all children and demonstrate behaviours consistent to the organization's vision, mission and goals.				
7. Methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible, and aimed at developing self-directed learners. Learners are equipped				
C. ACCOUNTABILITY AND CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT	4	3	2	1

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1. Roles and responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders.				
2. Achievement of goals is recognized based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system; gaps are addressed through appropriate action.				
3. The accountability system is owned by the community and is continuously enhanced to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community.				
4. Accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes are inclusive and collaboratively developed and agreed upon.				
5. Appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved and assessment results are contextualized to the learner and local situations and the attainment of the relevant life skills.				
6. Stakeholders are engaged in the development and operation of an appropriate accountability assessment system.				
7. School-community developed performance assessment is practiced and is the basis for improving monitoring and evaluation systems, providing technical assistance, and recognizing and refining plans.				
D. MANAGEMENT OF RESOURCES	4	3	2	1
1. Regular resource inventory is collaboratively undertaken by learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization.				
2. A regular dialogue for planning and resource programming, that is accessible and inclusive, continuously engage stakeholders and support implementation of community education plans.				
3. In place is a community-developed resource				

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management system that drives appropriate behaviours of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.				
4. Regular Monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management are collaboratively developed and implemented by the learning managers, facilitators and community stakeholders.				
5. There is a system that manages the network and linkages, which strengthens and sustains partnerships for improving resource management.				
6. Resource inventories are systematically developed and stakeholders are engaged in a collaborative process to make decisions on resource allocation and mobilization.				
7. An established system of partnership is managed and sustained by the stakeholders for continuous improvement of resource management.				

III. COPING MECHANISMS USED BY SCHOOL HEADS TO COPE WITH THE CHALLENGES

Directions: Kindly check the number to assess the appropriateness of coping mechanisms used by School Heads to cope with the challenges by using the scale below.

Legend:

- 4 High
- 3 Moderately High
- 2 Low
- 1 Very Low

A. PRODUCTION OF INSTRUCTIONAL MODULAR MATERIALS	4	3	2	1
1. The educational needs of learners were provided by the school				
2. The teachers received their needed materials in the delivery of basic education services				
3. The learners are given enough reading materials to help them cope up with the new modes of learning				

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS

4. The teachers were supported in the contextualization and localization of the learning materials				
5. The teachers were given technical assistance in the preparation, distribution and retrieval of activity sheets or self-learning modules				
6. The teachers were supported with the necessary materials in the preparation and reproduction of activity sheets or self-learning modules				
7. The teachers were able to meet increase in learning outcomes through the use of modules and online follow-up				
8. All subjects were given equal attention in the preparation and reproduction of activity sheets or self-learning modules, and in the development of other learning materials				
B. TRAINING OF TEACHERS	4	3	2	1
1. The school have provided trainings of teachers necessary in the pandemic situation				
2. The teachers attended trainings that would enhance their skills in the use of the different learning modalities				
3. The school specifically trained the teachers on the modes of learning being used in the school or division				
4. The school provided technical support and assistance to the teachers				
5. The teachers were given opportunities and choices in attending different trainings or webinars				
6. The school have given regular updates to learners, parents and teachers on the changing situations and immediate programs or projects				
7. The school coordinated the programs, projects, and new processes to all stakeholders				
8. There are meetings, webinars and sessions conducted to ensure updates to teachers				
C. PROVISION OF TECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS	4	3	2	1
1. The school through the division have provided technological materials and gadgets to learners				

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS

2. The school coordinated with the PTA and other school organization to support programs and projects necessary this pandemic				
3. The LGU and potential stakeholders supported the school in the provision of technological tools				
4. The school tapped the local officials in the municipalities, cities and province to help in providing technological tools				
5. The school allotted technological tools' procurement through the MOOE				
6. The school engaged the stakeholders in providing technological tools needed this pandemic				
7. There are regular conduct of meetings to inform parents of the changes in the teaching-learning schedule and modalities most especially in the use of gadgets				
8. The school purchased printers, gadgets and equipment necessary for learning				
D. PRODUCTION, DISTRIBUTION AND RETRIEVAL OF MODULES	4	3	2	1
1. The school resources were mostly used for the preparation and production of activity sheets or self-learning modules				
2. The school provided an enough space necessary for the production of learning modules				
3. The school coordinated with the local officials to help in the distribution and retrieval of modules				
4. There were assigned pick-up and drop-off areas for the distribution and retrieval of modules				
5. The school ensured regular announcement of schedules on the distribution and retrieval of modules				
6. The school required the teachers to create group chats with parents of learners to serve as communication venue for announcements and queries				
7. The school maintains its partnership with the community, local officials and other potential stakeholders to give smooth flow on the reproduction, distribution and retrieval of modules				
8. The school have provided trouble shooting mechanisms for learning modules that were not taken				

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS

and returned on time				
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-END-

APPENDIX B

Letter to Respondents

URDANETA CITY UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF GRADUATE AND ADVANCED STUDIES
San Vicente West, Urdaneta City, Pangasinan

Date _____

Dear Respondent,

The undersigned is a Doctor of Education major in Educational Management student at Urdaneta City University Graduate School, Urdaneta City who is working on a dissertation entitled “**CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS OF SCHOOL HEADS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC.**”

In this connection, I am soliciting your kind assistance to answer the questionnaire which has been carefully formulated. The data that you will provide will help elicit facts under this study.

Please answer the items honestly and rest assured that all answers will be held highly confidential.

Thank you and God Bless.

Very truly yours,

LORNA B. LEAL

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS

Researcher

APPENDIX C

QUESTIONNAIRE IN ESTABLISHING THE CONTENT VALIDITY OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Name (Optional):

Designation:

Direction: Read each statement in the evaluation sheet and rate each item using the scale below by putting a check (/) mark on the appropriate column of the evaluation sheet.

- 5 – Highly Valid - No flaws observed, anything more than to be desired to make it better
- 4 – Valid - Very little flaws are observed; minor recording of few items needed
- 3 – Moderately Valid- The overall usefulness is slightly diminished
- 2 – Fairly Valid - Several flaws are observed, overall usefulness is greatly diminished
- 1 – Not Valid - Major revision is needed to make it useful

CRITERIA	5	4	3	2	1
1. All the directions in the instrument is clear					
2. Each of the statement is clearly stated					
3. Each of the statement is readable					
4. The instrument is comprehensive; it covers all the areas that are important in the study					
5. The statement in each concept correspond to the subject matter					
6. The statement in each concept is consistent to reality					
7. The statement in each concept show a reasonable range of variation					
8. The statements are implicitly/explicitly formulated					
9. The statements are systematically arranged according to desirable sequence					
10. The statements do not overlap with each other and no duplication is observed					

CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISMS

Signature Over Printed Name